

Professionals' Collaboration on Strengthening the Teaching of History

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Abstract—This paper discusses the shared effort of teaching history in K-12 schools, community colleges, four-year colleges and universities to develop students' understanding of the history and habits of thought history. This study presents and discusses the problems of K-12 schools in colleges and universities, and the establishment of secondary school principals. This study also shows that the changing nature of practice can define new trends and affect the history professional in the classroom. There are many problems that historians and teachers of college faculty share in the history of high school teachers. History teachers can and should do better to get students in the classroom. History provides valuable insights into the information and embedded solid-state analysis models that are conflicting on the planet and are quickly changing exceptionally valuable. The survey results can reflect the history teaching in Malaysia.

Keywords—History issue, history teaching, school-university collaboration, history profession.

I. INTRODUCTION

CHARACTERIZING issues: Let us regard that every undergraduate who registers in and attends history classes will at some point in his or her life teach the content presented in those classes. Graduates could become engaged in government, using their historical knowledge to write legislation or present arguments for change. In business, they train workers or collaborating with colleagues to write documents. In a service capacity, they instruct learners overseas or locally in new technologies or about their own neighborhood structure and history. In the media, they produce or distributing information for a mass audience. In education, they teach young people who will carry the story on to future generations; or as parents, encouraging children to explore and learn [1].

Of those who take history courses during their K-12 or K-16 educational experience, very few students will finally major in history. However, the perspectives and modes of thoughtful judgment that historians believe are especially important to the understanding of history are required by all learners, no matter what their standard of educational achievement is. For a wider audience, the students in the 15,000 school systems across the United States college and university historians must also convey their teaching. A number of students they teach in college and university will

eventually go into classrooms to teach others. There are some of those university students who will be teachers to the next generation of students. As a result, they will influence their future students in terms of history knowledge and thought. As historians, they can build greater interest and a stronger commitment to the learning and teaching of history in middle schools by sharing with learners in university classes, not just the end result, but the very historical discovery and exploration process of the real data of the past, not just the conclusions of learning [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Issue of History Teaching Profession

There are many issues and concerns shared with all members of the teaching of history.

1. Students in High Schools and Colleges Often Do Not Realize the Breadth of the Field of History and Form of Presentation

They do not understand the complexity of this field; often believe that the answers have been determined. Since the 1960s, when the subject of the study of history broadened to include "social history," the new number and area of study materials available to researchers and history teachers has increased significantly. Data regarding minorities, women, workers, and children are more often presented in historical scholarship as part of the story. The new materials probate and census records, books of accounts, corporate memos, and employee records - is often analyzed by computer statistics program - during the first challenge for researchers and eventually the teacher. New forms of historical study are also sometimes suggested collaboration between academic disciplines. For example, emphasizing the economic and social classes together can connect to economists and historians. Employees and managers can take part in the historical and business departments. Research on women and social policy often puts women's studies and basic research on the same team [3].

Another important change in content and concept involves a growing movement to teach world history in schools. In this case, the current college curriculum may have less to offer the future of K-12 teachers of the right to social history. What is important is trainees would be more inclined to world history. Introduction of history course in schools is also attached with world history. But the world history content is still underestimated, especially at colleges that offer no course of world history at all, or related history courses which are more

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in depth study of world history for future teachers preparation in teaching and learning of history.

2. In the Course of the Study of History Is Necessary, There Is Imbalance between the Need for Content and Requirements for the Development of Critical Thinking, Writing and Historical Research Skills

The questions raised by these issues often become the focus of discussion among those who teach the course of the study, no matter what stage. Several solutions have been proposed to encourage different thinking about teaching and learning, resulting in an integrated curriculum model inspection. Peter Stearns [19] suggests taking a new look at historical content, asking the students to evaluate it for its ability to promote understanding instead of the traditional emphasis placed on "data point" and coverage. In his book, he emphasized the memory of recasting the teaching of culture and history [19]. His expertise is the use of literature interpretation to describe history events and examine topics in a global perspective. History department that trains teachers need to emphasize transferable habits of mind, from the assessment to document changes and causation assessment, and to provide appropriate basic content. Most studies of the social history of teaching standard are currently being developed in many countries including a growing emphasis on analytical skills specific discipline [20]. This opportunity may encourage some rethinking emphasis on curriculum and reading assignment in major history, so that future teachers gain experience over and over in developing habits of its mind (i.e., develop perspective and consider its reasons) and can identify them in the future of their own business teaching.

History teaches college courses on teacher evaluation model law. A lot of test in studying university courses can appear in the next generation of high school. Education Training courses will help understand and test a common method in learning history courses such as hands-on field experience. The real assessment will be an increasingly important part in the university classroom training range of historical imagination to the test of history in schools can contribute directly to the future [4].

3. When Students and High School Students Entered the History Classroom, They Often Have Little Background in History and Do Not Have a Background in Methodology

It is in the course of study that students often begin to develop or strengthen their ideas on a major college, and also the way in which the study of the history department get talented students to choose a major in history. One way to bring in these students is to create interesting programs for those students to find challenging and rewarding. To do so, a number of departments and faculties to make more use of primary sources, research and technology in the presentation, text analysis, and interdisciplinary courses that link English and history or anthropology and sociology. These solutions are discussed in college and university level to address the issue of content changes, parallel discussions and practice in the history of secondary education [5].

4. Secondary School History Teacher Has Many Students for Whom the High School Courses Will Be the Last Formal Exposure to History

These students, and college-bound students, have important reasons to get knowledge of history and can use effective methods of analysis. Studies show that the methods and materials are converted college history class every day in K-12 classrooms as the history of how it should be delivered. If college is the main method of communicating ideas, theories, and research data history, this, then, is a method that college students consider to be the appropriate one if they start teaching. Research also shows that college is not the most effective method of daily needs of diverse learners in school today. At least, the course must be combined with active discussions and exercises involving the use of historical materials and historical analysis [6].

5. Historical Content for Public

The national debate on the public agenda on compassion standard curriculum of K-12 and college historical materials is to enhance the public understanding of history knowledge. What information is important as it is to suggest how to provide effective learning basic questions referring to teachers at all levels of history. There are questions about who was educated in history field is needed to teach history in schools. The history trained teacher has to focus on strengthening the students to understand their history in K-12 classrooms. If one is aware of Bradley Commission, the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) or the proposed standard state documents, the need to improve the teaching of history is very important [7].

Many individuals and groups are not directly involved in historical research or teaching history, but they have taken an interest in what the "story" about the world and America. Following the announcement in 1994 by the National Science Standards, articles in newspapers such as the New York Times, Los Angeles Times and the Washington Post expanded discussion outside the exclusive jurisdiction of the historian to more public and political forum. In recent years, the conversation on campus has often centered on history knowledge. People who know about the research, teaching, and writing of history are more frequently drawn into public debate. There is book focuses on the debate about what students know and what they do not know about history has been in the bestseller lists. This public assessment of what needs to teach a history course should attract the attention of all historians, not only teachers from secondary schools should respond to the history textbook standard, but the textbook selection committee and parents too need to give their responses. The effectiveness as a historian and materials of history can affect the value of history to be seen increasingly vocal public, aware of, and interested [8].

In short, colleges, universities, and secondary school history faculty have the same objective, but they offer a variety of depth and breadth of knowledge, using a variety of techniques, and teach students with different populations. An individual who took a college course in history does not make him or her

historian because he or she needs to go further in depth study in history field. In fact, historian and university history teachers of secondary schools have the potential to create a symbiotic relationship forceful and productive which will benefit all teachers and students they teach. However, as Sarason et al. commented in their book, *The Preparation of Teachers*, "You need to know and experience in the most intimate and real situations that actions intended to affect" [9].

There is little time for secondary school teachers to pursue academic studies and college history without time to sit down in the classroom. Without any direct experience, however, it is possible to raise awareness and understanding and recognizing the issues important to the work of others.

III. METHODOLOGY

We used narrative literature to describe the current state of both art and science in the focus of this study. We used a literary narrative research to build the foundation of scientific knowledge. We collected all the important points in the discussion, and put them in here with reference to the particular field in which this paper was originally based.

IV. FINDINGS

A. *Issues in Secondary Schools*

We need to create a connection between the history in secondary schools and colleges that have lasting value. Further information on the history of university teaching of secondary school and growing recognition by both groups can increase the number of equations and, more importantly for students, the effectiveness of secondary school-university partnership.

B. *State and Local Curriculum Goals*

Schools were instructed, often with local curriculum or state-mandated, to "take" a lot of the problems faced by society in general. School curriculum specialists often including social issues such as race relations, youth violence, patriotism, civil rights, and family history or civics classes in history lesson. Classes such as "social problems" courses, leaving a serious study of the history behind to focus on current events and current issues taken from the evening news or weekly news magazine. However, background information that may have included historical knowledge on any of these topics is sadly lacking.

C. *History Standards Movement*

With "National Crisis Report," published in 1983, began to pay more attention to school learning materials [21]. 1980s, the examination showed that students of American students to be far behind the world in almost all other industrialized countries. The resulting political movement led to Educate America Act in 1994, which set national goals for student learning. One goal - which addressed the need for students to "leave grades 4, 8, [and] 12 has the competence to show more subject to challenge, including English, mathematics, science, foreign languages, civics and government, economics, arts,

history and geography ... "- a very real impact on the K-12 curriculum and history teachers [10].

As the history of standards development process has taken place, many of the issues that have emerged in the history of the profession over the past few decades have resurfaced. The "new" social history of working to the changing needs of schools and students, but it also brings forward the debate about what is "truth" and what young people need to know to meet the standards of National Goals. Cultural diversity and particularizes debate between pluralists, and between "traditional" and "new" historians. For some people, including new research and writing in historical texts mean that other important materials have been omitted. This debate has been heard in many countries as the curriculum to develop a standard history for the state [11].

D. *Schools Education and History Education*

In schools, they provide history expert teachers talk about the direction of running the teaching of history. Results are often about how to balance the content or methodology of how to prepare pre-service teachers with current and relevant knowledge, understanding students, schools, and the content is in the mode of constant change and rapid. Public education program needs to add a fifth year bachelor's degree for those who are interested in teacher certification to respond to the respective methodology. This change has been affected in some areas by the government's decision not to license any candidates for secondary teaching who do not have undergraduate academic major (i.e., not major in education). In other areas universities are considering significantly miniaturizing education schools into departments or programs or moving to graduate degrees only (which involve licensure needs) [12].

Since 1989, the agency has provided standards. National Board for Professional Teaching Standards (NBPTS) has begun to offer board certification for teachers, using the same model with the medical profession. (It varies from teacher licensing required by each state.) The NBPTS has developed high standards and strict depicting outstanding teaching. The volunteer process is growing in support among the states; there is a great increase in salary and recertification of teachers for the successful completion of the National Board process. NBPTS five core principles have also been adjusted by NCATE to be included in the evaluation of teacher preparation programs. The five principles are [4], [13]:

1. Teachers are committed to students' learning.
2. Teachers know subjects they teach and how to teach the subject to students.
3. The teacher responsible for the management and supervision of student learning
4. Teachers think systematically about their practice and learn from experience.
5. Teachers are members of learning communities.

Those standards, along with the standard Interstate New Teacher Assessment and Support Consortium (INTASC), are consolidating guidelines for teacher training institutions. State institutions are now offering seven areas of certification. A

certification area in history-social studies for early teenagers and young adults is predicted to be obtainable by fall 1998. AHA also provides guidelines for teacher supply line used by other organizations, and it has given recognition to the efforts NBPTS such as drafts in history-social studies.

History departments might helpfully take into account the fact that the guidelines can consider the relevance of their curriculum for teacher training. For the moment, with a few important exceptions, the specific duty rate of teacher preparation is left for the other units. But school education can only do so much without the cooperation of the university's history department and the school's history-social studies department. It appears that different regions hold pieces of the whole picture. A 1995 study by John W. Larner of Indiana University of Pennsylvania of 400 history departments found that in the history of the highest educational institutions, the task of tutoring history teachers is done outside history departments. The largest number of collaboration (35%) occurred in advising students' education, while as few as 8% contributed leadership for teaching the history-social studies methods course. Stronger cooperation in this area is that only one teacher can create stronger, better prepared students, more effective research, and a stronger future for history in academic institutions [14].

E. Theory of Learning and History Teaching

Several programs are underway to reflect this trend. Research in the field of second language learning and students propose a method that combines the skills of reading, writing [15], and analysis of the content to achieve "the goal" (what students know and what they can do) new standards are being developed in most states. A large number of immigrant children entering our schools in recent decades have drawn attention to questions about learning that had traditionally been inscribed other than with English-speaking students. Because school personnel today normally place newly accepted students in classes based on age rather than English ability, limited English-proficient (LEP) students are often placed in a high school class, where they must get language capability *and* content knowledge in effort to pass proficiency tests in history or government. Teaching students to be successful in this LEP involves the use of a more hands-on presentations, group learning, and alternative assessment. Vocabulary and concept is so important to the students' second language is equally important to all students of history; effective method for LEP students also found work for all its learners [15].

In other areas, increased use of computers in secondary schools for research and presentation, once the exclusive jurisdiction of advanced placement and gifted and talented classes, have routinely found guile "normal" and special needs students. Again, engage students in their own learning to improve learning for all students. In this area also, teachers often need training together with the students to become more comfortable with the possibilities for classroom use.

Recent research on the teaching of history also generates opportunities for mutual discussion and experimentation by

history teachers in the colleges and schools. This study is not yet well-connected with actual teaching practice, but the potential is important. Researchers have examined, for example, the way in which students handle material resources, with implications for more rapid generating revenue related analytical skills. Examples in Europe more active pedagogical relationship between researchers of history and history teachers may be more famous in the United States [16].

F. Successful Cooperation: School-University Partnerships

Although many believe [24] that the partnership between the university and high school faculty will improve the teaching and learning of history, often there is uncertainty about how to implement effective change. Part of this change involves awareness of what is being said and how efforts are trying to improve the role of history in our middle school classrooms, colleges, and universities.

In 1995, the American Council of the Learned (ACLS) created the Teaching Humanities: Journal of the ACLS Elementary and Project Development Secondary School Teachers Curriculum, stating that under the conditions of a rapidly changing science, "teachers must have a connection with a source of knowledge production and new interpretations ... often they are easily assembled in colleges and universities." This project supports humanities teaching in public schools through school-university collaboratives area. In addition, the ACLS has offered scholarships to sponsor individual sabbaticals for teachers who want to improve their content knowledge in the humanities [17].

The Ohio Academy created a model of [25] cooperation among secondary school history teacher and faculty of the university's history. The aim of this study is to link school teachers with faculty who can be a resource in the development field by providing knowledge in various fields of history. Commitment to their own institutions made frequent contacts difficult, but both sides appreciate the opportunity. In this case, the focus is on the individual needs of teachers, not necessarily directed at issues greater than the curriculum or learning.

The Philadelphia High School-College Collaborative joins [26] twenty high school and twenty faculties' college teachers to explore ways to teach the world history better and to provide new teachers. NEH-funded collaboration that began in 1993 has planned meetings twice a month to focus on topics of interest to all partners, updating the content of the textbook knowledge to the development of curriculum Philadelphia schools.

G. National History Standards Cooperation

After the 1989 conference of state governors, the 1994 progress of the Goals 2000: Educate America Act [23], and the recognition of main content areas in which students should meet standards, various states became concerned in projects to develop strong history standards for public school students.

Between the first and the most significant projects in the last decade has been the Project of Social Sciences California History [22]. Financed in part by NEH (National Endowment

for the Humanities) and by the state of California, the project has not only issued a curriculum framework (The California History-Social Science Framework, 1987) [22], which was adopted by the California State Board of Education. It also has a lot of teacher training programs, which (until funding was blocked) has been authorized to provide content and training in the use of the framework for all of California social studies teacher [4]. The task force designed a framework including university and school faculty, who work within the time frame to build the resources to implement the curriculum. Some of the members of the task force later became active in the development of the National Science Standards [18].

V. CONCLUSION

Historians should have the opportunity to see a multidimensional teaching in public schools. It is a special pleasure to obey the ways in which good teachers engage students in history. To see the excitement and energy of secondary school students to work on the construction of a society of medieval or develop colonial village can convince university historians' students' ability to think historically.

We need to overcome the perception that college and university historians have nothing to learn from the teachers of secondary schools. However, the dialogue should be conducted in two ways. Teachers a strong history of working with college students, but students still need to have a solid understanding of history [4]. While it is true that the history of the university have a deeper knowledge of the content of most teachers in secondary schools, they may not have experience with a variety of methods used by secondary teachers. Both sides have valuable knowledge to share. Cooperation curriculum is valuable. Seminar on content, new technologies and new historical research is valuable, but so is recognition by university historians setting where secondary school teachers work. Talking, listening, and brainstorming with teachers about the source of the best or the best approach to specific topics, communicate, or work with student-wiki all of particular interest to teachers and students of secondary schools and finally professor of history. This connection is perhaps most easily done through university education schools, which already has a relationship with the school. Public schools welcome friends who want to be part of the solution, to work with young people, and care that these students learn.

There are so many ways to get involved: to strengthen its history in our schools to work with teachers and secondary school students, with challenging jobs to do to reward creative teaching scholarship, by funding joint research to develop the new history and methods. Schools and students need help from people who have knowledge which enables the field robust content; universities need the cooperation of excellent teachers to engage students in a college-bound mystery and excitement of learning history. The results could be a reflection of the teaching of history in Malaysia.

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